

COPING WITH LONELINESS FOR SUSTAINABLE HEALTHY LIFE

Laveena D’Mello ¹, Joyson Prankey Cardoza ², & Sushmitha Kotian ³

¹ Professor, Institute of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0003-1935-002X; Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

² Research Scholar, Shrinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Email: joysoncardoza@gmail.com

³ Research Scholar, Shrinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Email: sush.m90@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Purpose:

Loneliness is universal and it’s both complex and unique to each individual. There has been no single common cause, for a child feeling no friends at school or lonely older adults whose life partner has recently died. This is the state of mind where people want human contact but feel alone. Some human beings want to be alone and they do not feel lonely. Some people are with people but still feel isolated and disconnected from others. The definition of loneliness has been described as being alone, a state of solitude of a mind. This causes them to feel empty, alone, and sometimes unwanted. It is very difficult for them to connect with others and they care for contact with people. In the long run, it affects Psychologically by social isolation, and introversion may lead to depression. This study discusses the term "lonely," its various causes, health consequences, symptoms, and its negative effects on both physical and mental health, and strategies for combating loneliness.

Methodology / design /approaches: In this research, both primary and secondary data are used in the analysis to overcome loneliness.

Findings and results: Loneliness can leave people feeling isolated and disconnected from others. It is a complex state of mind that can be caused by life changes, mental health conditions, poor self-esteem, and personality traits. Loneliness can also have serious health consequences including decreased mental wellness and physical problems. And coping mechanisms like self-love, concern towards others, organizing casual time, avoiding thinking too much about self, and more on spirituality will help to overcome.

Originality/value: Primary data with the interview, referred to the various articles and case studies and prepared the strategies for overcoming loneliness.

Type of paper: Primary and Secondary Research Analysis.

Keywords: Loneliness, Isolation, Mental wellness, Coping Mechanism, and Positive Thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Millions of us are suffering from one or the other form of loneliness. There are various signs of Loneliness like fear of attending social events, feeling irritated, spending too much time on a mobile or laptop, and physical symptoms like low energy, headaches, upset stomach, including diarrhea, constipation, aches, muscle pains, and chest pain. A lonely person always talks negative things about himself and others. The guilty feeling about themselves and also feel they are

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

responsible for the mistakes of others. They are not taking any initiative in any work because they feel that something will become wrong if they take initiative. They reduce speaking to others and prefer to stay salient. To avoid all these situations, they prefer to stay at home and sleep most of the time. There is a direct connection between loneliness with death, broken hearts, love failure, divorce, health, mental wellness, old age, and physical problems.

CAUSES OF LONELINESS

Age is no bar to loneliness but elderly or senior citizens are more prone to this. When children and young adults are moving to a new place for their education or career, they have to change their locality, house, and adjust to the new job, by teaming themselves for a new situation. It is quite difficult for them to interact with new people and make friends. They will break down and sometimes it is a suffocating situation for them. But gradually they have to overcome. Situational physical isolation, moving to a new condition, divorce death of the partner, or close family members and friends also lead to loneliness. In another case a person becomes very disappointed with a particular situation, generating a reflection of old memories when there is less work or no work to do to keep themselves busy. Emotions that were needed towards pet animals which will not be possible due to the death of the pet are also the cause of loneliness.

EFFECTS OF LONELINESS

Psychological stress and depression are the cause of people’s withdrawal from society. People will reduce their self-esteem and prefer to be isolated. It may affect people so much that they may develop the symptoms of depression. It will also affect people to lose hope and confidence in themselves. They believe others are much better than them. They may do mistakes and they fear the consequences, which pulls them to isolate themselves from others. Some even damage their life by consuming Alcohol and drugs, antisocial behavior, decreasing their memory, poor decision making, increasing stress, and sometime they may attempt suicide. Due to loneliness some young adults will increase their weight, have sleep disorders, and, not proper exercise to the body, and this will cause premature aging.

OBJECTIVES

A lot of people find themselves lonely. Yet many people simply find it too hard to overcome their isolation. This study discusses the term "lonely," its various causes, health consequences, symptoms, and its negative effects on both physical and mental health, and strategies for combating loneliness.

METHOD

The study is descriptive in nature. A total of 50 people were randomly selected from the simple random sampling method and also a secondary source was used. The age group is between 51-65 years of both the sex. The researcher developed a questionnaire and conducted direct interviews with the respondents to understand the problem, observe, know their opinion, assess the problem, and know their present situation and history, and also the coping strategies to overcome it.

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

FINDINGS

Loneliness Affects both Body and Mind: Apart from diseases, it could affect life which makes it difficult to accompany people.

N = 50	Percentage
Age (years) 51-55 = 20 56-60 = 13 61-65 = 17	Majority 51-55 = 40%
Sex Male = 19 Female = 31	Female = 62%
Marital Status Single = 2 Married = 41 Widow = 4 Divorced or separated = 3	Majority Married = 82%

- a) **Basic information:** including Age, Gender, and Marital Status. The researcher found the majority of the respondents are in the age group of 51 to 55 years which will increase as and when the age grows. The life cycle is the age of the parents working hard to launch their children and also to settle their children and they feel loneliness at this age. More than males, females feel lonely at this age and most of them are married and live with their partners but still, they feel lonely.
- b) **Feelings:** The majority of the respondents are feeling sad and empty (58%). They are developing an inability to feel pleasure including food habits, and entertainment.
- c) **Lack of energy:** Since they are not interested in festivals, celebrations, enjoyment, and cooking good food they develop a lack of energy which leads to lethargy in day-to-day life. About 62% of the respondents feel they lost interest in all the activities. This also leads (60%) to lead the concentration on the work they do.
- d) **Effect on physical and psychological Health:** 56% of the respondents express they have become so anxious that they have affected their bodies and mind. 58% have expressed that loneliness has lowered their motivation and confidence. The direct effect was on their sleep. 48% feel it is very difficult to get up from the bed and 50% find it hard to sleep. 36% will sleep too much. So, the effect of this, is that 48% of respondents have feelings of hopelessness.
- e) **Development of Habits:** The defense mechanism to overcome this problem, about 38% of the respondents have developed the habit of consuming alcohol, smoking, and another form of drugs as a substitute. And few respondents have become addicted to this too.

SUSTAINABLE HEALTH LIFE

Loneliness will affect physical health as well as Mental Health. There may not be many severe effects but feelings of detachment can lead to mental health disorders. People can develop physical pain, they may have an increased risk of dementia, risk of heart disease, which may lead to premature death. Loneliness also affects sleep and due to lack of sleep, restlessness, and

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

uneasiness lead to sleeping disorders and insomnia. Knowing all these effects on health there are a few tips to lead a sustainable healthy life. And are, (a) the people who think they are lonely have to understand the fact that they are lonely but cannot blame others for their loneliness and also not exaggerate that they are lonely. Thinking all the time they are lonely will still make the feeling strong. So being lonely does not repeat the feeling of loneliness, accept life as it is. (b) Healthy friendships with family members and friends, and understanding others’ needs and problems may help in reducing the pain of loneliness. (c) When your focus will divert from you to others who are in need, definitely suppress the thought of loneliness. Meet people who have similar problems. Those are the person who can understand you better and this can be the best coping strategy for a sustainable healthy life.

SUGGESTIONS

- Loneliness is painful, and everyone wants to come out of it. They wanted to be associated with others. The coping strategies are Accepting the limitation and reflecting on one’s thoughts. It simply recognizes and accepts how things are. Because the loss of a person will not come back, so accept the reality, whatever circumstances trouble us, accept it as it is. So be compassionate to yourself. Don’t deny loneliness.
- Instead of spending time alone, identify the inner strength, resources, and ability and involve others. Social support networks will help in sharing and connecting with others
- Religion and faith will help in providing support, spiritual growth, and connecting with other people with the same faith. Rituals, festivals, functions, and ceremonies will help in eradicating loneliness and create new opportunities for social contact.
- Visit people who need more support than us. There are people, who cannot repay your debt of good work, without expecting anything in return, like the senior citizens or disabled, differently abled, hard of speech and hard of hearing, disadvantaged sections of the society, people to lead a helping hand, Listening and empathizing will help in overcoming loneliness.
- Cultivate new friends and develop positive communication skills. Try to avoid those people who do not have a concern, or respect, or those who do not treat you well.
- Be happy, read a lot, and stop escaping by sleeping too much, overeating, watching too much TV, Mobile, the internet, and daydreaming to avoid loneliness.

CONCLUSION:

People will experience loneliness one or the other time. Its effects on physical as well as mental health. Most of the time is not under control but it can be manageable. Joining some classes or clubs will give us exposure to meet people and develop a sense of belonging. Strengthening the existing relationship will understand the people better. Pets are also loyal companions in loneliness. Self-love and care along with keeping always busy will be the way to a sustainable healthy life. And if you feel more stressed and more depressed then do not hesitate to meet the therapist to bring back to normal life.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Cohen, S., Doyle, W. J., Turner, R. B., Alper, C. M., & Skoner, D. P. (2003). Sociability and Susceptibility to The Common Cold. *Psychological Science*, 14, 389-395. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9280.01452>.
- [2] Cacioppo, S., Grippo, A. J., London, S., Goossens, L., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2015). Loneliness: Clinical Import and Interventions. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 10, 238-249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691615570616>.
- [3] Hawkey, L. C., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2010). Loneliness Matters: A Theoretical and Empirical Review of Consequences and Mechanisms. *Annals of Behavioural Medicine*, 40, 218-227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-010-9210-8>.
- [4] Rokach, A. (1988). Theoretical Approaches to Loneliness: From a Univariate to a Multidimensional Experience. *Review of Existential Psychology and Psychiatry*, 19, 225-254.
- [5] Maniaci, M. R. (2010). Are You Happy for Me? How Sharing Positive Events with Others Provide Personal and Interpersonal Benefits. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 99, 311-329. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018344>.
- [6] Rokach, A. (1990). Surviving and Coping with Loneliness. *The Journal of Psychology*, 124, 39-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1990.10543204>.
- [7] Rook, K. S. (1984). Promoting Social Bonding: Strategies for Helping the Lonely and Socially Isolated. *American Psychologist*, 39, 1389-1407. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.39.12.1389>.
- [8] Seepersad, S. S. (2015). Helping the “Poor Get Richer”—Successful Internet Loneliness Intervention Programs. In A. Sha’ked, & A. Rokach (Eds.), *Addressing Loneliness: Coping, Prevention and Clinical Interventions* (pp. 231-240, Vol. 1). New York: Routledge.
- [9] Schoenmakers, E. C., van Tilburg, T. G., & Fokkema, T. (2015). Problem-Focused and Emotion-Focused Coping Options and Loneliness: How Are They Related? *European Journal of Ageing*, 12, 153-161.
- [10] Rokach, A. (1989). Antecedents of Loneliness: A Factorial Analysis. *Journal of Psychology*, 123, 369-384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1989.10542992>.
- [11] Vidya N. and Laveena Dmello (2021). An Approach to explore the determinants of Elder Abuse: A case study conducted in Dakshina Kannada District. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJRSSH)*, ISSN: 2547-7831, 08(01), 27-32.
- [12] Thejavathi U.C. and Laveena Dmello (2021). Depression in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management, (IJRESM)*, ISSN: 2582-5792, 04(03), 12-16.
- [13] Varghese Evin and D’Mello Laveena (2021). A Study on Positive Parenting and Parent-Child Relationship. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science, (IRJMET)*, ISSN: 2582-5208, 03(03), 1042-1048.
- [14] U.C. Thejavathi, Laveena D’Mello, and K.T. Shwetha (2021). Effectiveness of Positive Therapy in Management of Stress, Anxiety, and Depression Along with Improvement in Quality of Life Among Chronic Kidney Disease Patients- A Review Based Analysis *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management (IJRESM)*,

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

ISSN (Online): 2581-5792, 4 (12), 101-106.

- [15] DMello Laveena, Monteiro Meena (2016). Age-Related Problems of the Elderly and Their Coping Mechanisms. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 723-729, ISSN (Online): 2455 – 4200.
- [16] D’Mello Laveena. B. M. Govindaraju, Monteiro Meena (2016). A Study on the Challenges Faced by Single Parent on Teenager Care. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET)*, 1(1), 54-59, ISSN (Online): 2456 – 4664.
- [17] Pinto Vincent and Laveena D’Mello (2019). Institutionalized Elderly Women-Issues & Concerns. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)* 3(1), DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586231>, 6-12.
- [18] victor C, Sullivan MP, Woodbridge R, Thomas M. Dancing with loneliness in later life: a pilot study mapping seasonal variations. *Open Psychol J* 2015; 8: 97-104.
- [19] Pettite T, Mallow J, Barnes E, Petrone A, Barr T, Theeke L. A systematic review of loneliness and common chronic physical conditions in adults. *Open Psychol J* 2015; 8: 113-32.